

Cold gas in distant galaxies

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The formation and evolution of galaxies over cosmic time is a complex process that involves physics on a vast range of different scales: from the accretion of gas from the cosmic web onto galaxies, down to the formation of stars deep inside cold clouds of molecular gas. The cycle of matter flowing in-and-out of galaxies and stars is called the baryon cycle. Constraining the total amount of material that is captured in the different phases of the baryon cycle at different cosmic epochs is critical for our understanding of galaxy formation. Great progress has been made on this front observationally and the cosmic evolution of the mass density in stars and atomic hydrogen, as well as the star formation rate density are now broadly known out to $z \sim 4$ (e.g., [1]). One of the main missing pieces of this puzzle, however, is the cosmic density of cold molecular (H_2) gas. This phase is key, being most directly connected to the star formation. Constraining the cosmic molecular gas density has been a major effort in recent years on large interferometers (NOEMA, VLA and ALMA) and have recently culminated in the ALMA Spectroscopic Survey of the Hubble Ultra Deep Field (ASPECS).

ALMA Spectroscopic Survey of the HUDF

ASPECS is a three dimensional survey of the deepest region of the Hubble Ultra Deep Field (HUDF; [2, 3]). It is the first extragalactic large programme with ALMA and designed to provide a flux-limited census of the cosmic molecular gas and dust. This is achieved by scanning the complete ALMA 3.0 mm and 1.2 mm bands for the emission from carbon monoxide (CO) and other tracers of the molecular gas (e.g., [C I]) as well as the dust continuum emission. The main data products from ASPECS are two datacubes that contain the line and continuum emission. The depth and wide frequency coverage result in a very high continuum sensitivity and the dust continuum map at 1.2 mm reaches an unprecedented $9.3 \mu\text{Jy beam}^{-1}$, revealing dozens of dust-rich galaxies in the HUDF ([4]). The ASPECS survey is complete and the reduced and calibrated data products and catalogs have been released[§].

Gas mass-selected galaxies

Here, we focus on the gas emission and start by answering what is perhaps the most simple question that one can ask given a survey like ASPECS: which galaxies harbour the cold molecular gas? All the bright emission lines that are detected in the ASPECS data can be uniquely associated with galaxies at $z = 1 - 4$ that are detected in the Hubble Space Telescope and multi-wavelength imaging. Instrumental for the identification are also the deep VLT/MUSE observations from the MUSE GTO survey ([5]), that provide redshifts and metallicities for many galaxies. The galaxies show a variety of morphologies, ranging from compact and/or clumpy structures, to more

extended disks. The star formation rates of the galaxies place them above, on and also, interestingly, below the typical star formation rates at a given stellar mass and redshift (the so-called ‘galaxy main sequence’). The latter sources are particularly important, as these galaxies would not normally be selected for follow-up observations in targeted surveys, but are key to get a complete census of the molecular gas. Overall, we find that ASPECS detects roughly half of all the galaxies in the HUDF above a stellar mass of $10^{10} M_{\odot}$ at $1 < z < 2$ and $10^{10.5} M_{\odot}$ at $2 < z < 3$ ([6]).

Figure 1: Modelled CO excitation ladders (normalised and colored by redshift) for the gas mass-selected galaxies from the ASPECS survey ([7]). The galaxies at $2 < z < 3$ show on-average higher gas excitation than those at $1 < z < 2$, suggesting an intrinsic evolution in the ISM conditions with redshift. Understanding the variations in the gas excitation conditions with galaxy properties is essential to infer the total mass in cold gas and the boundary conditions for star formation.

Conditions in the cold interstellar medium

The conditions in the cold interstellar medium of the galaxies are important, because they set the boundary conditions for the fragmentation of the molecular clouds and the onset of star formation. Furthermore, they impact the conversion factors required to convert the observed line emission to a total molecular gas mass, especially when only excited states of CO are observable (which is common at higher redshifts). On average, the MUSE spectra show the sources at $1 < z < 2$ have roughly solar metallicity, motivating the choice of a galactic CO-to- H_2 conversion factor. By modeling the multi-line CO, [C I] and dust continuum measurements for all the ASPECS sources using radiative transfer models, the overall excitation of the sources can be constrained (see Figure 1). We find that the ASPECS galaxies at $z = 1 - 2$ show

[§]<https://www.aspecs.info> and <https://almascience.org/alma-data/lp/ASPECS>

a range in excitation in their mid- J lines that on-average lies above that of the Milky Way, but below that of earlier sub-millimeter-selected sources at similar redshifts (that have higher IR luminosities). The sources at $2 < z < 3$ show more highly excited gas than those at lower redshift. Interestingly, none of the lower redshift sources show excitation as high as the average of the galaxies at $2 < z < 3$, even though the cosmic volume probed is similar to within a factor of 2. This suggests there is an intrinsic evolution in the excitation conditions, where galaxies at higher redshift have on-average more highly excited gas, potentially due to their higher (surface) densities of star formation rate and molecular gas ([7]).

Pushing to higher redshifts

The large number of redshifts from Lyman- α at $z \geq 3$ from the MUSE HUDF Survey provides a unique opportunity to push the sensitivity of ASPECS at $z = 3-4$ through stacking. To this end, we performed a survey of all the brightest ($H < 26$ AB magnitude) star-forming galaxies in the MUSE HUDF at these redshifts with VLT/KMOS and Keck/MOSFIRE, to get their systemic redshifts (as Ly α itself is typically seen offset from the systemic velocity). We do not detect emission from CO, [C I] or dust in the stacks, which is consistent with the expected gas fractions from scaling relations, but only for a substantially higher gas and dust mass-to-light ratios than seen in the Milky Way. Such conversion factors are in agreement with the significantly sub-solar metallicity of the galaxies on average ($12 + \log(O/H) \approx 7.8$; median $\log M_* [M_\odot] = 10^{9.1}$), but emphasise that it may become increasingly challenging to detect cold gas with classical tracers in typical star-forming galaxies at $z > 3$ ([8]).

Cosmic molecular gas density and the baryon cycle

Through a statistical analysis of all the molecular line emission in the datacubes, ASPECS provides unprecedented constraints on the cosmic evolution of the molecular gas density. The density of molecular gas increases from high redshift up to a peak at $z \sim 1.5$, followed by a decline of a factor ~ 6 to the present. This evolution is overall similar to the evolution of the cosmic star formation rate density and suggests that the evolution of the star formation rate is to first order driven by the availability of molecular gas ([9]).

The evolution of the cosmic molecular gas (H_2) density can be combined with the evolution of the stellar

mass, star formation rate and HI density, to constrain the evolution of baryons associated with galaxies averaged over time and space. Interesting results that arises from this are that the stellar mass density increases over time and exceeds the total gas density in HI and H_2 by $z \sim 1.5$. As the subsequent decline in the molecular gas density between $z \sim 1.5$ and the present is insufficient to account for the growth in stellar mass over the same time period, this implies that additional accretion of gas into the cold molecular medium has to take place ([1]).

Future directions

ASPECS provides unprecedented constraints on the overall molecular gas and dust content of galaxies averaged over space and time, and follow-up work is ongoing to refine and dissect the measurements in different ways. This includes enlarging the cosmic volume that is probed to further constrain cosmic variance (cf. WIDE ASPECS). The constraints on the cold gas masses are only as good as our understanding of the conditions inside the cold interstellar medium. To date, there is still a limited understanding of the CO excitation in typical star-forming galaxies around cosmic noon and future multi-frequency studies observations of different tracers will better anchor the gas mass measurements. Apart from this, ASPECS was designed to maximise the sensitivity for molecular gas and the observations are therefore unresolved. Now that the gas-rich galaxies in the HUDF are pinpointed, resolved follow-up observations will be able to further constrain the gas dynamics in the galaxies. In all these cases, facilities such as ALMA, NOEMA and (later) the ngVLA will play a key role. Together with the upcoming extensive observations of the HUDF from the the James Webb Space Telescope, these will soon provide an even more detailed picture of the evolution of the cosmic gas fractions in galaxies out to cosmic noon and beyond.

References

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